

Aerogels – the so-called ‘Fourth State of Matter’

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Extremely low density gels of silica and other metal oxides can be prepared by the removal of the water/alcohols from the aqua- or alco-gels under supercritical conditions. The use of alkyl orthosilicates suggested by Teichner as precursors, has made the technology of preparing aerogels much simpler. In this article a very brief account is presented for the preparation of simple and heterometal alkoxides, developed in the laboratories of Mehrotra, and their applications for the preparation of novel aerogels by the sol-gel process.

Aerogels are extremely light materials with density as low as 0.01 g cm^{-3} and surface area as high as $1500 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$. With such a high proportion (even upto 99%) of air in a highly porous framework of silica (or other metal oxides), aerogels are extremely useful in applications, such as (i) superinsulating spacers in windows as well as covers for passive use of solar energy, (ii) acoustic impedance matching in piezoelectric devices, and (iii) more effective catalysts¹⁻⁴, in view of their large surface areas for chemical reactions to occur.

A revolutionary simple technique for the preparation of aerogels was suggested by Kistler⁵ in 1931. The common aquagels or algogels are generally prepared from the corresponding sols (with the appropriate dispersing medium, e.g. water or alcohol) by removal of the liquid phase. During the evaporation of the solvent, the surface tension of the liquid creates a concave meniscus in the capillaries. Under hydrostatic pressures ($P = 2\sigma/r$: where σ is the surface tension of the liquid, e.g. $7.2 \times 10^{-2} \text{ nm}^{-1}$ for water and r the radius of the capillary, say, 1 nm) of the order of 1500 atm, the body of the gel (an ensemble of capillaries) would tend to collapse, shrink or become more compact, resulting in cracks or fragmentations during the drying process. An ingenious device to overcome the above shrinking due to surface tension effects was provided by Kistler⁵, who suggested the removal of the ‘liquid’ under supercritical temperature and pressure con-

ditions, so that the liquid meniscus and its interfacial tension could be avoided. Under such circumstances, extremely low density gels with their structures filled with air were obtained and thus, began the era of aerogels.

Following the preparation of aerogels from aquagels, Kistler replaced water in aquagels with alcohol which was finally removed under supercritical conditions. For example, the silica, precipitated in the following type of reaction,

was washed free from chloride, which itself was a rather tedious process and required the hardening of the silica by ‘ageing’ to avoid clogging the pores of the filter. Replacement of water by alcohol in a soxhlet type extractor was also a very cumbersome process.

However, being interested in preparation of high porosity matrices as adsorbents for rocket propellents, Nicolaon and Teichner⁶ introduced the use of silicon methoxide,

The advantages of this process are so obvious. In this new procedure no inorganic anions are involved and algogels are obtained directly from the sol of the hydroxide in methanol. The technology has

been considerably improved by Henning and Svensson⁷, Tewari *et al.*⁸, Graser and Strange⁹, Armor and Carlson¹⁰, Cheng *et al.*¹¹, Pekala *et al.*¹² and Fricke^{1,2}.

Although the nature of the liquid has been changed from water to alcohol⁵ and later to liquid carbon dioxide⁸, supercritical removal of the liquid from the gel has remained a key-step in aerogel technology. In fact, the term aerogel itself is considered synonymous with a material made by supercritical drying technique, which has been extended even for the preparation of organic aerogels, e.g. from the polymerisation of resorcinol with formaldehyde as precursors¹².

Alkoxides as precursors for aerogels : The distinct advantages (e.g. control of pH and range of solubility in alcohols) in the use of metal alkoxides¹³ and even more so, of heterometal alkoxides^{14,15} as precursors for the conventional sol-gel processes, have already been well established¹⁶, but these have been shown^{4,17} to be even more important for aerogels in view of the serious difficulties in the original Kistler's procedure⁵. Teichner¹⁷ demonstrated the facile applicability of the method to the preparation of mixed metal oxide aerogels,

Incidentally, a large number of heterometal alkoxides have been synthesised in the research school of Mehrotra and a brief description of the possibilities for their use in the preparation of mixed metal aerogels has been emphasised in a recent plenary lecture at the Third International Conference on Aerogels¹⁸ held at Wurzburg in 1991, which was preceded by two other international conferences^{19,20} of the series.

The main purpose of this article is to bring to the notice of chemists in general a novel type of materials, description of which is still almost limited to such journals of material science which do not attract the attention of chemists. Further developments in the domain of aerogels require penetrating studies of physical, inorganic and organic

chemists in addition to material scientists. In addition, a few references³¹⁻³⁶, to the growing literature on heterometallic alkoxides which are an unique contribution from the laboratories of the author, are enumerated with only one case being cited as illustrative example :

The final aerogel has been shown to be an excellent catalyst for a number of hydrogenation type reactions in a number of preliminary studies. In fact, the potential of these studies on heterometal alkoxides has been shown to provide multi(2, 3 or 4)-metal oxides as extremely efficient catalyst surfaces for a variety of organic reactions.

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